

Rain and wind climate co-variation relevant to estimating blade erosion from a climate perspective

Abhiram Vinod, Krystallia Dimitriadou, Charlotte Hasager

4/15/2026, 15 April 2026, DTU, Risø Campus, Roskilde

Content

- Leading-edge erosion introduction (IEA Task 46)
- Damage model
- Climate perspective
- Meteorological data
- Results

IEA Task 46 Erosion of Wind Turbine Blades

- Operating Agent: Charlotte Hasager, Co-operating Agent: Christian Bak, DTU Wind

Elevator Pitch

- Eroded blades need repair
- Eroded blades cause AEP loss
- Tip speed and rain climates are drivers

The work plan is delivered by 47 organizations from 12 countries:

- 1 certification body
- 5 wind farm owners
- 2 consultancy
- 5 wind turbine manufacturers
- 10 coating manufacturers
- 23 academic/R&D organizations

Country	Contracting Party	Participant Organization
Belgium	Belgian Ministry of Economy	Engie
Canada	Natural Resources Canada	WEICan
Denmark	Danish Energy Agency	DTU , Hempel, Ørsted, PowerCurve, Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy, SP Tinby
Finland	Business Finland	VTT
Germany	Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy	Fraunhofer IWES , Emil Frei (Freilacke), Nordex Energy SE, Mankiewicz, RWE, Henkel, Fraunhofer IFAM
Ireland	Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland	South East Technological University, University of Galway, University of Limerick
Japan	New Energy and Industrial Technology Development Organization	AIST, Osaka University, Tokyo Gas Co. Asahi Rubber Inc., CRIEPI, Industrial Technology Institute Fukushima prefectural government, Niigata University
Netherlands	Netherlands Enterprise Agency	TU Delft, TNO, Suzlon
Norway	Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate	University of Bergen, Statkraft
Spain	Centre for Energy, Environmental and Technological Research	Aerox, CENER, DNV Iberica, Nordex Energy Spain, Universidad Cardenal Herrera - CEU
UK	Offshore Renewable Energy Catapult	ORE Catapult, University of Bristol, Lancaster University, Imperial College, Vestas UK, Ilosta, Armour Edge, AkzoNobel
US	US Department of Energy	Cornell University, Sandia National Laboratories, 3M

Rain Erosion Tester and VN-curve

Source: Bech et al. Renewable Energy, 2022; and Hannesdóttir *et al.* 2024

Impingement of Rain on Turbine Blade

Damage rate (D) is Proportional to

Velocity (V)

$$\dot{D}_j \propto V^{6.7},$$

Rain rate (I)

$$\dot{D}_j \propto I^2,$$

Eisenberg *et al.* Wind Energy, 2018

Climate Perspectives

Climate Trends in Precipitation for Denmark 150 years

Source: DMI Klimastatus 2025.

Annual Precipitation Amounts and Trends (42 years)

ERA5 | Annual Precipitation | 1981-2023 | Long-Term Trends
all: $a=0$ | $b=0$ | $p=1.00$

Decreasing trends over Western Europe and increasing trends over the Mediterranean.

Precipitation Trends in Europe (42 years)

Annual Precipitation: 1981-2023

CORDEX:
Co-ordinated
Regional
Climate
Downscaling
Experiment

Source:
Peter
Hoffman

Climate Trends in Wind Speed

- Neither mean wind speed or frequency of storms have changed during the observation years in Denmark (Source: DMI 2025)
- Wind-index (Source: EMD) <https://www.vindstat.dk/>
- Some global models indicate stilling towards 2100 in a warmer climate
- Statistics on the co-variance of rain and wind at climate scale (> 30 years) is not existing to our knowledge

Our study sites

Data sources

- Risø rain gauge
- Risø wind speed from meteorological mast
 - Period, temporal resolution: 2002 to 2025, 10 minutes
- GPM IMERG rainfall. GPM stands for the Global Precipitation Measurement satellite mission, and IMERG stands for Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for GPM (Huffmann et al., 2023). The IMERG precipitation estimates can be separated into probabilistic contributions from liquid and solid hydrometeors, reflecting the likelihood of each precipitation type.
 - Period, temporal resolution, spatial resolution: 2014-2023, 30 minutes, 11 km
- New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) wind speeds
 - Period, temporal resolution, spatial resolution: 2014-2023, 30 minutes, 3 km

IMERG example

Alaiz IMERG 10 Year

Buseco IMERG 10 Year

Levenmouth IMERG 10 Year

Rézentières IMERG 10 Year

San Gregorio IMERG 10 Year

Båtskär IMERG 10 Year

Moray East IMERG 10 Year

Risø Rain Gauge and Meteorological Mast Wind Speed

- Tipping bucket, 10 minute data

- Cup anemometer, 10 minute data at 125 m

Precipitation, Wind Speed and Spearman Correlation for 19 Years (Risø)

End of incubation for 19 years (Risø)

Copula Parameter for the UK and Ireland (5 years)

- Results are based on 5 years satellite product IMERG rainfall and 5 years of NEWA wind speeds (2020-2024).

- Source: Visbech *et al.* Renewable Energy (2025)

19 year End of incubation sensitivity analysis

Erosion Safe Operation

Uncertainties due to weather

EOI varies from ~4 to 6 years

Uncertainties due to weather and input test data

EOI varies from ~1 to 12 years

References

- Bech, J.I., Johansen, N. F.-J., Madsen, M.B. Hannesdóttir, Á., and Hasager, C. B. (2022) Experimental study on the effect of drop size in rain erosion test and on lifetime prediction of wind turbine blades. *Renewable Energy*, 197, 776-789. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.06.127>
- DMI (2025) Klimastatus 2025. DMI Report 25-15. https://www.dmi.dk/fileadmin/NCKF/Rapporter/NCKF_-_Klimastatus_2025.pdf
- EMD <https://www.vindstat.dk/>
- Eisenberg D, Laustsen S, Stege J. Wind turbine blade coating leading edge rain erosion model: Development and validation. *Wind Energy*. 2018;21:942–951. <https://doi.org/10.1002/we.2200>
- Hannesdóttir, Á., Kral, S. T., Reuder, J., & Hasager, C. B. (2024). Rain erosion atlas for wind turbine blades based on ERA5 and NORA3 for Scandinavia. *Results in Engineering*, 22, Article 102010. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2024.102010>
- Hoffman, Peter, Explaining long-term trend patterns of precipitation over Europe, <https://www.pik-potsdam.de/~peterh/marpit/RD2S/rd2s.html.pdf>
- Huffman, G.J., Bolvin, D.T., Joyce, R., Kelley, O.A., Nelkin, E.J., Tan, J., Watters, D.C., West, B.J., 2023. *Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) Technical Documentation*. Technical Report, NASA Goddard Space Flight Center.
- NEWA. New European Wind Atlas. DTU: Roskilde, Denmark, 2024. Available online: <https://www.neweuropeanwindatlas.eu/>
- Visbech, J., Hasager, C. B., Göçmen, T., & Réthoré, P.-E. (2025). Copula-based joint distributions of rain and wind for leading edge erosion risk atlas. *Renewable Energy*, 253, Article 123358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.123358>

Acknowledgements

- IEA Wind Task 46 Phase 2 <https://iea-wind.org/task46/>
- EUDP IEA Task 46 Grant 134243-532862
- AIRE project European Union under the grant agreement 101083716.

DTU

